

Review Study on Bruhaniya Mahakashaya of Charaka Samhita

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ABSTRACT: In Charaka Samhita, drug is an important part of chikitsa chatushpada, which has been mentioned next to the physician. The patient cannot be treated properly without the knowledge of the drug. Brihan chikitsa is considered to be the greatest treatment for Karshya and disorders associated with Karshya in Ayurveda. This is because Brihan karma works to increase all of the body's dhatu. Bruhaniya mahakashaya is one of the 50 mahakashaya, which have been mentioned in Charaka Samhita Sutrasthana. Each mahakashaya contains ten drugs. In Brihaniya mahakashaya drugs such as Ksirini, Rajksavakak, Ashwagandha, Kakoli, Kshirkakoli, Vatyayani, Bhdraudani, Bhardwaji, payasya, Rsyagandha are included. Each medication works well to treat karshya. The present paper deals with the review of above ten drugs and mode of action of drug. According to comparisons made using the Brihan mahakashaya drugs like Ashwagandha and Rishyagandha have nearly identical qualities. According to samanya siddhant, all of the medications- sweet taste, cold in potency and madhura vipaka- increased jala and prithvi bhuyoshyith dhatu because of the drug's domination over pruthvi and jala.

KEYWORDS: Brihaniya Mahakashaya, Charaka Samhita, Upyuktanga, jala mahabhut

INTRODUCTION

Brihatryi is the most well-known literature in Ayurveda is a compilation of the three important Charak Samhita, Sushrut Samhita, and Ashtang Hridayam, and contains the fundamental principles of Ayurveda and is used to treat illnesses. In the Charak Samhita, Brihan chikitsa is mentioned by Acharya Charak as Langhanbrihaniya adhyaya[1] and is explained by Acharya Vagbhat as dvividhopkramaniya adhyay[2] in the Athang Hridayam. There are two types of therapies in dvividhopkramaya. Treatments come in two varieties, just like the upakramyasya (that is to be treated). Samatarpan and Apatarpana are the names of the first, while brumhana and langhans are their respective synonyms [3]. Brihana is for nourishing, while langhana is for body-lightening. The mean of the person or the body to be treated is known as "Upakramya". Diseases too are of two categories Sama and Nirama. For a sthula person or a Sama disease. Apatarpan or langhana are the best treatments, whereas a thin person or a Nirama disease should take Samatarpana[4] or Brihana. All therapies and treatments fall under one of these two categories. Brihan karma also reduces Vata and Vata-Pitta. According to Charak, Bruhan chikitsa" is defined as "whatever the corpulence of the body is. "The drugs characteristics are" heavy cold so unctuous thick bulky slimy sluggish stable and smoothly."[5]. This work comprises the detailed description of the drugs under Bruhaniya Mahakashaya, an effort to rule out the controversies regarding some of the drugs under this varga with the help of the available literatures, commentary on Charaka samhita, Nighantus and explain Brihan karma and their mode of action in body.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Etymology of Brihan

When 'brihdhatu' joins with the 'Atipratyay formation of 'Brihat' word, it indicates (strong), powerful, and Purnavikasit (complete develop). Brihan or is derived from the word "brih," which means growth and increase^[6]

Definition from different Acharya

Brihan Chikitsa is define as whatever the corpulence of the body is Brihan chikitsa . Acharya vagbhata, Brihan is concept which is increase of the body mass it called Brihan. Brihankarma also alleviates Vata and Vat-Pitta^[7]

Benefits and indications

The brihana karma (stoutening therapy) is recommended for people who are weak due to illness, medications (such as those in Panchkarma therapies), and alcohol (drinking) , sexual activity (with women), grief, covering long distances, suffering from chest injuries, pregnant women, carrying heavy loads. In the summer, Brihan should also be administered to healthy individuals. Brihan therapy makes a person strong, cherished, and heals diseases that can be cured ^[8]. Charak Samhita and Ashtang Sangrah refers to the medication for brihan as Mahakashaya in chapters titled Shadverechaniya Adhyaya and Mahakashaya Sangraham Adhyaya, respectively however all Acharya of the brihatryi declared that mansa flesh) is the greatest brihan dravya^[9]

Table no.1: Classification of drug in Ayurveda

Drug name	Charak (mahakashaya)	Sushrut (Gana)	Bhavaprakash nighantu
Ashwagandha	Brihaniya, Balya, Shool prashaman	Roppanevam Utsadanvarg	Vajikarak in Mishrakvarga
Kakoli	Brihaniya, Balya, jivniya, Snehopag, AngPrasadan, Shukrajanan	Kakolyadi Gana	AshtaVarga
Ksheer-kakoli	Jivniya, Brihaniya, Shukrajanan, Snehopag	Kakolyadi Gana	Ashtavarga
Bala	Brihaniya, Balya, Prajasthapan	-	-
Vidhari	Brihaniya	Shyamadiganha	-

Ashwagandha (withenia somnifera)^[10]

Ashwagandha is mentioned in the different Samhita like Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Astanga hridayam, Chakradatta and Nighantus etc.

SYNOMYMS

Sanskrit -Hayagandhi, Vijigandhi

INGREDIENTS

Alkaloids and with anolides, anahygrine, trepanise, anaferinine, tropinine anaferinine, tropinine

CONSTITUENTS

Alkaloids and with anolides, anahygrine, tropinineana ferinine

PROPERTIES AND ACTION

Rasa - Tikta, Kashaya

Guna - Laghu

Virya: Ushna

Vipaka - Madhura

Karma- Vatakaphapaha, Balya, Rasayana, Vajikarana

IMPORTANT FORMULATIONS

Ashvagandhadyaria, Ashvagandhadi Lehya, Balvagandhalakadi Taila

UPYUKTANGA- Dried mature roots

THERAPEUTIC USES

Kshaya ,Durablya. Vataroga, Shotha, Klaihya, Excessive emaciation, balsasosa, Insomnia

DOSE-3-6 gm powdered drugs for

Action and Use of Ashwagandha (withenia somnifera)

1. Dosh Function

Function- Kaphshamak

Use-Kaph Vataj Vikar

2. External function

Function- Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic

Use- Galgand, Granishoth, Vatvyadhi

3. Internal Function

Function-Mastishk Shamak

Use-Bhram, Anidra, murchchha

4. Digestive system

Function- Deepan, Pachan, Anuloman, Analgesic, antihelmenthic

Use- Udarshool, Vishtambh

5. Circulatory system

Function-Blood purifier, anti-inflammatory

Use- Oedema, blood disease

6. Respiratory system

Function-Decrease of cough, antiAsthmatics

Use-Cough, Asthma

7. Reproductive system

Function- Uveitis, Vajikaran, Vaginitis

Use- Weakness of uterus muscle

8. Urinary System

Function- Diuretic

Use- Mutraghat

9. Special use

Function- Balya, brihan, rasayan

Use- Anti-inflammatory, Kshay, balshosh

2. Kakoli ^[11]

Kakoli is made up of the dried tuberous root of *Roscoea procera* D.Don (Fam. Liliaceae) a plant that grows from 1800 to 3000 metres in the Western temperate Himalayas, from kumaon to Kashmir.

SYNONYMS-

Sanskrit: Vayasoli, Svadumanisi

CONSTITUENTS-Sugar

PROPERTIES AND ACTION-

Rasa: Madhuru

Guna : Sheet, Guru

Virya: Sheet

Vipaka: Madhurs

Karma: Pittahara, Vatahara, Sukrala

IMPORTANT FORMULATIONS

Brihat Ashwagandhadi Ghrit, Brihitchhagaladi ghrit, Dashmoolarishta, Shivagutika, Amritaprasha Ghrit

THERAPEUTIC USES- Raktapitta Shosa, jvara, Shwasa , Kasa, Kshaya, Daha

DOSE-3-6g

Action and Use of Kakoli (*Roscoea procera*)^[12]

Dosh Function

Function- Vatapitta Shamak

Use-Vatpittavikar

External function

Function- analgesic

Use-Vatapittaruja

Internal Function

Function- Jvaragna

Use-Daha, Jvara

Circulatory System

Function- Strength Promoter

Use- Rakta pitta, Hridroga, Raktaroga

Respiratory system

Function- Swashghan

Use- Shwasa, Kasa

Reproductive System

Function- Sukrala

Use- Yonivyapat

Special Use- Shosa, Rasayana

Ksheer Kakoli ^[13]

Ksheer Kakoli dried whole bulb is used to make Ksheer Kakoli (*Lilium polyphyllum* Lin.) (Fam. Liliaceae), a glabrous herb growing 6-34 m tall in the Western temperate Himalayas from Kumaon to Kashmir at an altitude of altitude of 2500-4000 m; boiled

SYNONYMS

Sanskrit: Shukla, Ksheervallika

English: Fritillary

CONSTITUTENTS: Peimiphine and Peimitidine

PROPERTIES AND ACTION

Rasa: Madhur

Guna: Guru, Snigdha

Virya: Sheet

Vipaka: Madhura

Karma :Vatahara, pittahara, Brimhan, Rasayana, Vrishya, Shukravardhak, Kaphakarak, Trishnahara, Stanyajanana, Basti Vishodhani, Vishaghna

IMPORTANT FORMULATIONS

Dashmoolrishta, Shivagutika Brihatphala Ghrita, Brihat Guduchi Taila, Brihatmasa Taila

THERAPEUTIC USES

Raktapitta, Daha, Raktaroga, Shosha, Jvara, Hridroga, Yonivyapat, Vatavyadhi, Vatapittaruja, Shwasa, Kasa Vatarakta

DOSE-3-5 g in the power

Action and Use of Ksheer Kakoli (*Lilium polyphyllum*) ^[14]

Dosha Function

Function- Vatapitta shamak

Use- Vatpittavikar

External function

Function-analgesic

Use-Vatpittaruja

Internal Function

Function- Jvaragna

Use-Daha, jvara

Circulatory System

Function: Strength Promoter

Use: Rakt pitta, Hridroga, Raktaroga

Respiratory system

Function: Swashghan

Use: Shwasa, Kasa

Reproductive System

Function: Sukrala

Use: Yonivyapat

Special Use: Shosa, Rasayana

BALAA^[15]

Sida cordifolia is the botanical name for bala. It IS a perennial herb that reaches a height of 30 m. Its leaves are 2.5 cm long and 2.3-5 cm wide with 6-7veins and are oblong or oval in shape. Its leaves are heart –shaped, serrate and truncate.

Synonyms

Latin name: Sida cordifolia

Common name: Country mallow, Heart-leaf sida

Sanskrit name- Baladaya, Badiyalaka, Bala

CONSTITUENTS- Ephidrine, Ral acid, mucine, phytosterol

Rasapanchak

Rasa- madhura

Guna – Laghu, Snigdha

Veerya- Sheeta

Vipak- Madhura

Prabhav- Balya, Rasayan, Bruhan

Formulations – Balaadi kwath, Chandanbalaalakshadi Tail, Balaadya Ghrit

Therapeutic Use- Kshay Rog, Daurbalya

Dose- 3-5g in the powder form.

Action and Use of Bala (Sida Cardifolia)^[16]

Dosh Function

Dosha- Vat pitta shamak

Use- Vat pitta Vikar

External function

Function- Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic

Use- Inflammation, Eye Disease

Internal Function

Function- Neuro-strength promoter

Use- Paralysis, facial paralysis and vata Disorder

Digestive system

Function- Grahi

Use- Grahani Disease

Circulatory system

Function- Cardio-strength promoter

Use- Weakness in heart, Raktpitta, Chest trauma

Reproductive system

Function- Spermeto-poiticprocreants

Use- Metrorrhagia endomitriosis

Urinary system

Function- Diuretic

Use- Mutrakricha

Special Use

Function- Balya , Rasayan, Bruhan

Use- Daurbalya, Kshay, Balshosh, Inflammation

Vidhari^[17]

Synonyms

Sanskrit: Viidhadaraka

English: Elephant creeper, Baby wood- rose. Elephant-climber

PROPERTIES AND ACTION

Rasa: Katu, Tikta, Kasaya

Guna: Laghu, snigdha

Veerya : Ushma

Vipak : Madhur

Karma: Kaphavatahara, Adhobhagahara, Rasayana, ayurvirdhikara, Medhya, Balya, Svarya, Agnikara, Kantikara, Rucya

Formulations of Importance - Misraka Sneha

Therapeutic Action-

Gulma (abdominal tumor), Mutrakriccha (pain in urination), Aruchi(anorexia), Hridruja (pain in chest region), Anaha (abdominal distention), Udavarta (gaseous distention), Arsa (piles), Udara (ascites), Shula, Vataruja, Grahabadha, Vatarakta, Raktapitta, Sopha, Amavata, Vatarsh, Krimi, Svayathu, Meha, Unmada, Apasmara (epilepsy), Pandu, Ksaya, Kasa

Dose: 3-5g

Action and Use of 'Viidhadaraka (Argyreianervosa)^[18]

Dosh Function

Function: Kaphvatashamak

Use: Kaphvatvikar

External Function

Function: Wound Healing

Use: Inflammation and open wound

Internal Function

Function : Tonic for neurons

Use: Vata disorder, brain Disorder

Digestive system

Function: Mild laxative. digestive, digestive stimulator

Use: Indigestion, constipation, Haemorrhoid

Circulatory system

Function: Anti-inflammation, heart tonic

Use: Cardiac disorder

Respiratory system

Function: Kanthya, Kaphghna

Use: Cough hoarseness voice

Reproductive system

Function: Sperm poetic, Anti-inflammation

Use: Leucorrhoea, Debility of Sperma

Urinary system

Function: Anti-diuretic

Use: Prameha

Special use

Function-Balya, Rasayan

Use- Karshya, nutrition disorder

DISCUSSION

Almost all of the drugs stated in the brihaniya mahakashaya Madhura Rasa, Guru, Snigdha guna, Seeta virya and Madhura vipaka. Except for Ashwagandha, vrudhdaru, Dugdhika

Madhura's Functions^[19]

The functions of Madhura rasa include rasadi sapta dhatu vardhaka, ojovardhaka, sense organ nutrition, Balakara, Bruhan, Sthariyakara and stnyavardhaka. The panchbhautic composition of Madhura rasa is prithvi and jala.

Seetha Virya's^[20]

Seetha Virya's functions include prahladana, Sthirikiran, jeevan, Balya, Prasadana, Stambhana and Kledana. Shitavirya's panchbhautic composition is dominated by Jalamahabhuta.

Madhura Vipaka's Purpose^[21]

On Dhatu, Madhura rasa acts as a shukral, while on Dosha, it acts as Vata-pittahara, Kapha-varhdhana. Vipaka Madhura Predominance of Prithvi-jala in panchbhautic composition

Function of Guru-snigdha Picchila guna

The Guru's gunas are Brihana, Balakrit, Pustikrit, Vrushya, and Kaphvardhaka. The panchbhautic makeup of guru guna is dominated by Prithvi-jala

Snigdha has four gunas: balya, snehana, marávavrushya and Kaphavardhaka. The jala predominates in the Snigdha guna's panchbhautic makeup

Picchila guna is jeevaniya, Balya, Guru, and Kaphavardhaka. Picchila guna's panchautic composition has jala predominance. The qualities of the drug are determined by its bhautic constitution.

The parthiva dravyas are upchaya (development), sanghata (compactness), guruta (heaviness), and sthirta (firmness) the apyadravyas are sneha (unction) and mardav (softening).

Based on these details, we were able to come to a conclusion, illustrating how these medications work under the brihana mahakashaya, demonstrating brihana activity.

CONCLUSION

Brimhana Dravya predominantly comprises of parthiva and Apya Bhavas and vatapittahara properties. Prithvi jala dominates the panchbhautic constitution of guruguna. Brimhana means proportionate body composition mainly through kapha, Mamsa, Meda that leads to proper development of different body part. Brimhana Dravya's mode of action can be accessed on the ground of its Gunapachaka. The ingredients in it mostly have predominance of Guru, Snigdha, Shita and Manda Guna, Madhura Rasa and Madhura vipaka that causes Brimhana effect. Apart from this some of the drugs in brmhaniya mahakashaya have tikta kashaya rasa, Laghu, Tikta guna, Ushna virya, Katu vipaka that helps in regularize the Agni leading to increase metabolism. Upchaya (development), sanghata (compactness), guruta (heaviness), and sthirta are the parthiva dravyas (firmness) Sneha (unction) and mardav are the apvadravyas (softening). We were able to come to a conclusion based on these details, demonstrating how these drugs work under the brihana mahakashaya, demonstrating Brihana activity. So Acharya Charak mentioned one drug repeated in another group on the basis of rasa, guna, virya, vipak, Prabhav, and its function according amayik prayog. During treatment of karshya one should be cautious that Brimhana Dravya's used in such instances should be laghu santarpana in nature because already in an emaciated person Sharirbala and Agnibala are reduced. Some drugs act by clearing strotas and correcting agnibala and other nourishes all dhatus.

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